

Research

Knowledge of Diabetic Patients Type2 Toward Diabetes and Diet and its Relationship with HbA_{1c} Levels

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Abstract: Type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) has become a public health problem that seriously influences patients' quality of life. Identification of the level of knowledge related to diabetes among the general public is essential in strategies for prevention of diabetes mellitus. This study aims to assess the baseline levels of knowledge and its relation with glycated hemoglobin (HbA_{1c}) level in diabetic patients in Taiz. The study was conducted on forty individuals with type2 diabetes of both sexes and used a questionnaire for data collection from Yemeni population than find the relationship between knowledge and HbA_{1c}, blood glucose (BG) and Body Mass Index (BMI). Results showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the knowledge, HbA_{1c}, BG, and BMI between the samples studied, where demonstrated that 5% of samples was knowledge above 68 % and had a lower HbA_{1c} level less than 6, also shown that 40% of the samples was knowledge 60 % with an average of HbA_{1c} level 8%. In comparison, 32.5% of samples were knowledge less than 50% and had a high average HbA_{1c} level 11%, also found there is a relationship between knowledge and BG, BMI, even the knowledge on the disease for males (52.81%) better than females (47.19%). Type2 diabetic patients have a decrease in knowledge, and this affects levels of HbA_{1c} and BG, even who has good and moderate knowledge, not reflected on their attitudes towards HbA_{1c} and BG.

Keywords: Diabetics type2; HbA_{1c}; Knowledge; BG; BMI.

Introduction

Several cases of diabetes globally are projected to be around 347 million, World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that diabetes will be the 7th leading cause of death by 2030, more than 80% of them prevailing in low- and middle- income countries [1].

Lifestyle-related diseases like diabetes mellitus have emerged as a significant public health problem [2]. Diabetes has become a public health problem that seriously influences patients' quality of life. Diabetes is a chronic disease where patient's ability for self-management is essential, so it is a model of chronic illness which demands many lifestyle changes from patients and also their active role in the management [3].

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic disorder of glucose metabolism resulting from dysfunction of pancreatic beta cells and insulin resistance, which accounts for a high incidence of morbidity leads to various events, including micro and macrovascular complications. Diabetes is characterized by a state of chronic hyperglycemia resulting from a diversity of etiologies, environmental, and genetic acting jointly [2-4]. It is now a global epidemic with devastating humanitarian, social and economic consequences [1].

Determination of the glycated hemoglobin (HbA_{1c}) level is the standard gold method of evaluating glycemic control in patients with diabetes. Also the maintaining the HbA_{1c} level at <7% can significantly reduce the risk of diabetes complications and improve the prognosis. Therefore, patients with diabetes are required to change their lifestyle based on their blood glucose levels and follow a specific treatment regimen to effectively control their fasting blood glucose and postprandial glucose levels [5].

Optimal blood glucose control in diabetes can be achieved through strict adherence to the medications, diet and exercise, this, in turn, will minimize the long-term complications [6]. Therefore, some studies show that the primary goal of diabetes treatment is to maintain blood glucose levels close to normal range [7].

Unfortunately, there is still insufficient awareness about the real aspect of the problem. There is lack of knowledge about the existing interventions for preventing diabetes and the management of its complications. Besides, there is a need to increase knowledge regarding diabetes and its complications as it has significant benefits including an increase in adherence to treatment, thereby decreasing the difficulties associated with diabetes [8]. Hence, this study aims to assess the baseline levels of knowledge and its relation with HbA_{1c} level in diabetic patients in Taiz.

Materials and methods

Specimens collect:

The study was conducted in Taiz, Yemen, Almudaffer and Al-qahera districts from May 2019 to September 2019, forty individuals with type2 diabetes after (2h) from eating of both sexes of age from 16 To 70 years. The portion of males was 51% (21\40) and females 49% (19\40).

Questionnaire:

The data were obtained using a questionnaire completed during face to face interviews [9]. The questionnaire for data collection was consisted of 2 parts, the first part on the socio-demographic information, nutritional history, and anthropometric of the patient. In contrast, the second part of the questionnaire was on the knowledge related to diabetes, where the questionnaire consisted of 37 questions.

Chemicals and Machine:

Spectrophotometer (type721) (China), blood glucose monitoring system (China, 2014), Vortex shaker, weight Balance (model:- China),meter, Alcohol pad 70%, EDTA Tube, disposable syringe 5ml/cc, tips (blue & yellow), micropipette (500ml, 100ml, 20ml, 10ml) and glycohemoglobin (model:- SGMitalia company).

Body mass index (kg/m²):

Based on the body mass index (BMI), patients were classified as underweight (less 18 kg/m²), normal weight (18 - 24 kg/m²), overweigh (25 - 29 kg/m²), obese (29 - 32 kg/m²) and excessive obesity (≥ 32 kg/m²) [10].

Blood glucose test (mg\dl):

Blood glucose test ware measured according to [11]. The equipment was checked with quality control samples before each measurement.

Glycohemoglobin test HbA_{1c} levels (%):

Glycohemoglobin test HbA_{1c} levels were measured according to the kit of Glycohemoglobin test by using the Spectrophotometer (type721) and Glycohemoglobin test (model:- SGMitalia company). The levels of HbA_{1c} was according to American Diabetes Association, and the HbA_{1c} level is less than 5.7% the levels have been in the normal range, if HbA_{1c} level is between 5.7% and less than 6.5% the levels have been in the prediabetes range and if HbA_{1c} level of 6.5% or higher the levels were in the diabetes range.

Calculation:

For each sample and for the calibrator, calculate the ratio (R) of the glycohemoglobin absorbance to the total hemoglobin absorbance.

$$1 - Free = \frac{Abs\ T}{Abs\ STN} \times Con.\ St\ D$$

$$2 - Total = \frac{Abs\ T}{Abs\ STD} \times Con.\ St\ D$$

$$A - HbA_{1c} = \frac{Free}{Total}$$

$R\ (Sample) / R\ (Cal) \times conc.\ Cal = Glycohemoglobin\ HbA_{1c}\ (\%)$

Statistical analysis:

Statistical methods were used to calculate means and standard deviations of three simultaneous assays carried out for some test. Statistical analysis by (IBM SPSS Statistics 24) was applied to the data to determine differences ($P < 0.05$) performed by ANOVA.

Results and discussion:

This study is the first study in Yemen - Taiz to report on knowledge, and practice related to diabetes among the general public, and its relationship with HbA_{1c} levels. Of this questionnaire were noteworthy findings that majority had either moderate knowledge on diabetes, level of knowledge was significantly associated with HbA_{1c}, BG and BMI on diabetes, our study also revealed that the gender had significant association with knowledge on diabetes. This finding also different to most other studies conducted in developing countries [12] where males were found to have better knowledge of the disease than females.

Knowledge:

Knowledge about diabetes mellitus, appropriate attitude and practices are vital to reduce the incidence and morbidity associated with DM [13]. Knowledge and education is a keystone for diabetes care and unless adequate knowledge and education are given self-care essential for diabetes management is not possible, hence increasing access to diagnosis, self-care, self-management education and affordable and quality treatment are vital components of the response. However, there is still insufficient awareness about the problem and lack of knowledge about the existing interventions for preventing diabetes and the management of its complications [1]. So noted from figure 1 and table 1 that there significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the knowledge

between the samples studied, also the same table shown that ratio of the mean of knowledge ranged between (31.3 - 76.11%).

Figure 1. Mean of knowledge of samples

In addition, the study showed that there no significant differences in knowledge between some of the samples studied, which averaged knowledge was 55.2% for samples (35, 2 and 20) and between samples (14, 21, 23 and 24) which averaged knowledge was 50.70%. In addition, there were no significant differences in knowledge between the samples (5, 25), (16, 15), (7, 29) and (32, 34) where the mean of knowledge was 49.30, 46.30, 41.8 and 38.8% respectively.

Table 1. Mean and standard deviation of knowledge and HbA_{1c} of samples

	Range	Sample	Mean ± SD
Knowledge %	76.11 - 62.00	7	68.64 ± 4.39a
	59.70 - 50.70	14	53.33 ± 2.54b
	49.30 - 40.33	13	45.09 ± 4.20c
	39.00 - 31.30	6	35.67 ± 3.70d
HbA _{1c} %	4.40 - 6.13	3	5.52 ± 0.97a
	7.09 - 8.82	17	8.19 ± 0.58b
	9.03 - 10.95	12	9.88 ± 0.54b
	11.20 - 13.78	8	11.94 ± 0.84c

Table 1 shown that 17% of samples were had good knowledge of 68.64%, while 35 % of samples had moderate, but 47.5% had poor knowledge. Figure 2 shown that 52.5% of the studied samples had a mean knowledge of more than 50%, while 32.5% of the samples had mean knowledges between (40 - 49%). Also 15% of the samples had a mean knowledge between 30-

39%. Unlike most studies from developing countries which reported poor knowledge of diabetes among the general public, where shows that the levels of knowledge are comparatively better with the majority (>50%) having either moderate knowledge [14]. The lack of positive knowledge could be an important obstacle for long term management of diabetes. This study agrees with a study conducted by Rani PK et al., suggested that knowledge, language and religion are interdependent factors associated with knowledge of diabetes [15]. The study showed that males were found to have better knowledge on the disease (52.81%) than females (47.19%), similar to many other studies [16] and this study agrees with Shah VN et al., where found that males were found to have better knowledge on the disease than females [12]. Also, with Fatih Ozcelik where shown that patients with lower education level (elementary school) had a significantly lower knowledge score compared with those with higher education (high school, university) [13].

Figure 2. Percentages of knowledge

HbA_{1c}:

HbA_{1c} is a standard clinical assessment of glycemia and the basis of most data relating glycemic control to complications [17]. HbA_{1c}, the major form of stable glycosylated Hb, is the product of a slow and mostly irreversible reaction that occurs throughout the life span of the erythrocyte, HbA_{1c}, has been understood that HbA_{1c} reflects mean BG levels over the previous 2-3 months. It has been proposed as a diagnostic criterion for diabetes, and the other approach routinely used to assess glycemic control, provides quite different information [10]. Table 1 and figure 3 shown significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the HbA_{1c} between the samples studied, where the mean of HbA_{1c} ranged between (4.4 - 13.79%), although some samples did not have significant differences

such as samples 13 and 32) and samples (38,11,35,37,18 and 39) at the level of significance ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Mean of HbA_{1c} of samples

Figure 4 shows that a very low percentage 7.5 % of samples studied was the mean of HbA_{1c} less than 6, while the 42.5% of samples was HbA_{1c} between (7- 8 %). In addition, the 30% of the samples was the average of the HbA_{1c} between (9 - 10 %) and 20% of samples were HbA_{1c} between (11-13%).

Figure 4. Percentages of HbA_{1c} level

Therefore the figures 3 and 4 shows that more samples were HbA_{1c} more than 7 %, where there some studies show that maintaining the HbA_{1c} level at <7% can significantly reduce the risk

of diabetes complications and improve the prognosis, however, to achieve such a goal, patients with diabetes are required to change their lifestyle based on their blood glucose levels and follow a specific treatment regimen to effectively control their fasting blood glucose and postprandial glucose levels [18].

Figure 5 show that the mean 5% of samples was knowledge above 68 % and had a lower HbA_{1c} level less than 6, while 32.5% of samples was knowledge less than 50% and had a high average HbA_{1c} (9-13%) as average 11%. Also showed that 40% of the samples had an average knowledge between (50-68%) as average 60 % with of HbA_{1c} ranged between (7-9%) as average 8%. There was a strong negative correlation between knowledge and HbA_{1c}. In this study is also evidenced that the highest percentage of patients increased their HbA_{1c} rate and the result of low knowledge.

Figure 5 The relationship between knowledge and HbA_{1c} level

This indicates that the lower the rate of knowledge in patients the higher the HbA_{1c} rate, where this study agree with some studies which indicates that the lower the rate of knowledge in patients the higher the HbA_{1c} rate, because they are not more successful in controlling diabetes and following their diet, and vice versa [13-19]. These results also agree with a study conducted by Hawthorne K et al, to assess the effectiveness of culturally appropriate diabetes health education and knowledge on important outcome measures in type 2 diabetes concluded that this appears to have short term effects on glycaemic control and knowledge of diabetes and healthy lifestyles [20]. Although there are some samples of HbA_{1c} was ranged (7 - 8) and had a relatively low rate up to

40%, and the reason may be the impact of some drugs regulating sugar. In addition, some samples had an HbA_{1c} between (7- 8), although the rate of knowledge is high up to more than 60% and We think the reason is that they did not adhere to the medicines not and adequately follow the diets for people with diabetes.

The most notable finding in our study is the gap between knowledge of diabetes and its relationship with HbA_{1c} Levels. Even though the 17% of samples had good knowledge and the majority 52 % had moderate knowledge, but it is not reflected on their attitudes where about 92.5 % from samples were found to have a poor attitude towards HbA_{1c}. Many previous studies in a similar setting to Sri Lanka have reported poor attitudes [21]. Although two samples number (26, 36) had a high knowledge rate (76.11 and 72.2), however, there is an increase in the average HbA_{1c} was (8.8 and 9%), respectively. We think the reason is due to non-adherence to the diet or failure to take medications at the appropriate doses and the correct timing. In contrast, samples (32, 1, 18 and 38) found their rate of knowledge is lower of the 40% and had averaged HbA_{1c} was (6.1, 8.6, 8.2 and 7.9) respectively we think the reason is the use of glucocorticoids.

Our study showed that better glycemic control and reduced the complications is achieved when the level of patients' knowledge about diabetes is high. Thus, it is essential to educate patients about diabetes, its complications, treatment, and self-care [22].

Blood glucose (BG):

Blood glucose was maintained within this narrow range by factors which control glucose production and glucose utilization [23].

Figure 6. Mean of BG of samples

Although HbA_{1c} is widely accepted as a useful index of mean blood glucose in the treatment of patients with diabetes, its use as a screening test for diabetes has been controversial, because HbA_{1c} testing can be performed at any time of day and without special patient preparation. However, some studies have suggested that HbA_{1c} may not be a suitable screening test because of low sensitivity; others have suggested the opposite [24]. It is important that the relationship between daily patients monitored blood glucose determinations. Besides, HbA_{1c} be clearly defined to enable patients and their health care providers to set appropriate daily BG testing goals to achieve HbA_{1c} levels representing low risks for adverse outcomes [25].

Figure 6 and Table 2 indicates that there significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in blood sugar between samples where the mean of BG ranged between (107-555 mg\dl). Although there is a difference between the study samples in blood sugar and maybe the reason for their use of drugs for sugar.

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of BG and BMI of samples

	Range	Sample	Mean \pm SD
BG (mg \dl)	107	2	107 \pm 0.00a
	119 - 155	7	135.14 \pm 9.39b
	157 - 555	31	311.42 \pm 116.81c
BMI kg/m ²	Less 18	3	15.90 \pm 1.06 a
	18 – 24.9	20	22.62 \pm 1.73 b
	25 – 29.9	14	26.85 \pm 1.34 c
	30 – 40	3	35.78 \pm 4.31 d

Figure 7 found that a low rate of 5% of the samples had an average blood glucose of less than 107 mg\dl when the knowledge ranged between (50-55%) as average (52.5%). In comparison, the proportion of samples increased to 12.5% when the blood sugar ranged between (119-155 mg\dl) at the rate of knowledge ranged (41-50%) as average (45%). The percentage of samples increased to 62.5% when they ranged between (157-555 mg\dl) at a knowledge rate ranging between (31-40%) as average (35%). These values indicate that there is a high 62.5% among people with diabetes, whose blood sugar is still too high, while a very low percentage (5%) of patients has an average blood sugar with a minimum of the less normal range. Moreover, a low percentage of 12.5% has average blood sugar in the normal range. We can infer that there is a

relationship between knowledge and BG. The higher the knowledge, the lower the rate of hypoglycemia was normal and the lower the knowledge, the higher the rate of blood sugar [11].

Our study cleared that there is a lack of knowledge and neglect in patients of high blood sugar and cumulative sugar, which is identical to the high rate of lack of knowledge. Our results agree with a study conducted by McPherson ML et al. to determine the relationship between patients knowledge about their blood glucose control, observed that patients with greater understanding and knowledge better glycaemic control [26]. Also agree with J C Petrie et al. were showed that HbA_{1c} and BG levels were significantly lower and the knowledge level was significantly higher in patients who received diabetes education compared with those who did not [19]. In addition, this study agrees with Thomas G et al. were showed a stronger correlation between the knowledge level and HbA_{1c} levels than between the knowledge level and BG in type2 diabetes [11].

Figure 7. The relationship between knowledge and blood glucose level

BMI:

The Body Mass Index (BMI) is the dominant means of defining and diagnosing obesity in national and international public health policy [27]. It is the ratio of body weight to height (wt (kg) / ht (m²)), it is also known as Quetelet's index, it is highly correlated with body fat, the WHO has cut off points for determining whether individuals are underweight, regular, overweight /obese, high BMI (> 30) is associated with increased risk of chronic diseases as DM.

Table 2 and figure 8 shows that there statistically significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between the samples studied, where BMI ranged was between (14.7 – 40 kg/m²).

Figure 8. The BMI of samples

Figure 9. The Range (BMI) of samples

Figure 9 , tables 1 and 2 showed that 7.5% of samples in the BMI is low (less 18 kg/m²) and was their knowledge (35 to 43%) and their HbA_{1c} between (7-9) , while the high rate of

samples 50.5% was has BMI (18 - 24.9 kg/m²) and their knowledge was (55- 67 %) and their HbA_{1c} was (4.4 - 8) , despite their is presence of overweight and excessive obesity 35% and 7.5% on respectively, where was BMI between (25 - 29.9 kg/m²) and (30 - 40 kg/m²) on respectively, and their knowledge was (41 to 55%) and (38 to 41%) on respectively ,while their HbA_{1c} was (6 - 10) and (6 - 13) on respectively, this suggests that the obesity factor is not the only cause of high rate of HbA_{1c} and hyperglycemia because other factors may affect it before knowledge, but Fatih Ozcelik, et al. shown that there is a weak positive significant correlation between BMI and HbA_{1c} and the positive correlation between the BMI and HbA_{1c} levels and negative between the BMI and knowledge level further support our findings [13].

Conclusion

Diabetic patient's type2 have a decrease in knowledge, and this has an effect on high levels of HbA_{1c} and BG, even who has the excellent and moderate knowledge, not reflected on their attitudes towards HbA_{1c} and BG. There is a correlation between patient's knowledge levels and high HbA_{1c}, BG and BMI, but there is a weak positive significant correlation between knowledge and BMI. Also, the knowledge of the disease for males better than females.

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nutrition. In this time, we are
interested in examining
traditional fermented
products (milk and cheese)
and vegetables for the
presence of Lactic acid
bacteria producing
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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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